

Hotel stays of individuals with a visual impairment: a qualitative study with a focus on sensory substitution

Saroosh Bilal, Jorge Rebate, David M. Jacobs & Verónica Sevillano

To cite this article: Saroosh Bilal, Jorge Rebate, David M. Jacobs & Verónica Sevillano (2025) Hotel stays of individuals with a visual impairment: a qualitative study with a focus on sensory substitution, *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*, 20:8, 2885-2901, DOI: [10.1080/17483107.2025.2511982](https://doi.org/10.1080/17483107.2025.2511982)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17483107.2025.2511982>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

Published online: 11 Jun 2025.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

Article views: 854

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Hotel stays of individuals with a visual impairment: a qualitative study with a focus on sensory substitution

Saroosh Bilal^a

^aFacultad de Psicología, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain; ^bAccesibilidad Universal e Innovación, Fundación ONCE, Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

Sensory substitution devices (SSDs) hold the potential to assist individuals with a visual impairment with actions such as navigation and orientation. Even so, SSDs are not frequently used in everyday life. The lack of user involvement in the development of SSDs may be among the reasons for this discrepancy. To remedy the gap, this study explores the challenges that are encountered by individuals with a visual impairment in a situation in which SSDs may be particularly useful: the hotel environment. Semi-structured interviews conducted with eight individuals revealed three main themes: navigation and orientation challenges and strategies, wayfinding aids, and user needs. The findings highlight substantial challenges due to accessibility, localization, spatial configuration, obstacles, and dependency on others. Navigation strategies employed by the individuals included exploration, the use of mental maps, environmental cues, and asking for spatial directions. Whereas SSDs were considered to have future potential, issues of precision and information overload were common concerns. The study revealed a need of individuals for autonomy, control, and sociability, which is in line with the basic human needs proposed by Deci and Ryan in their self-determination theory. Overall, our findings underscore the importance of tailoring SSDs to the specific challenges that are encountered by individuals with a visual impairment. Furthermore, it is important to consider SSDs in the broader context of the needs of individuals, because the satisfaction of needs promotes people's well-being and motivation to use SSDs.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 21 December 2024
Revised 12 May 2025
Accepted 21 May 2025

KEYWORDS

Hotel environments;
intrinsic motivation;
mobility aids; sensory
substitution;
user-centered design;
visual impairment

> IMPLICATIONS FOR REHABILITATION

- Sensory substitution devices (SSDs) hold the potential to aid individuals with a visual impairment
- To be effective, SSDs should be adapted to the needs and challenges of end users
- Individuals with a visual impairment were asked about their experiences in hotel environments
- Needs and challenges were identified that allow more effective designs of SSDs

Individuals with a visual impairment often encounter navigation and orientation challenges that are due to their visual condition. Dealing with such challenges may in some cases be facilitated by sensory substitution devices (SSDs), which are devices that detect information through one sensory modality and present it to users through another sensory modality. As described in the historical review by Ptito et al. [1], the first SSDs that became well-known in the scientific community detected light intensity with a camera and presented this information to users through vibrations [2]. A wide variety of SSDs has followed the early ones [3]. Current SSDs may capture information based on light intensity [4], infrared sensors [5], sound waves [6], or magnetic information [7], among other possibilities. In the majority of cases, the SSDs present the (transformed)

information to users with sounds [8], vibrotactile stimulation [9], or electrotactile stimulation [10].

In recent years, scientific research has shown an increase in the use of SSDs that are based on information about the distance to the surfaces and objects that surround the user, which may be captured by infrared cameras [11]. In contrast to light-intensity-based information (as captured by regular cameras), distance-based information does not depend on the color and shading of surfaces. Distance-based information may therefore provide a more intuitive basis for sensory substitution. Likewise, providing information to users through vibrotactile stimulation is relatively common in recent SSDs. Haptic stimulation has the advantage that the skin is often underused as a sense organ, whereas audition is indispensable for a large number

CONTACT David M. Jacobs david.jacobs@uam.es

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group
This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

of daily tasks such as orientation, communication, and others [12; cf. 1, p. 3]. In line with these observations, our opinion is that coupling distance information to vibrotactile actuators is a promising route for SSDs that aim to support navigation and orientation.

In laboratories, SSDs that transform detected distance to vibration have proven to be useful for walking toward targets [13], avoiding obstacles [14], stepping on boxes [15], detecting apertures [16], or grasping nearby objects [17]. Moreover, the devices are relatively cheap and comfortable [11], they are often described as being intuitive even for unexperienced users [12], and the possibilities that they offer to users may further increase with training [18,19]. Even so, relatively few individuals with a visual impairment rely on SSDs for navigation and orientation in their daily lives [19]. In this sense, the situation of SSDs is different from mainstream aids such as tablets and smartphones, which are progressively replacing the use of at least some traditional aids [20]. In general, often-mentioned factors that contribute to the limited use of technological aids include high costs, difficulties with repairs and maintenance, and social stigma. Specifically for SSDs, it has also been argued that potential end-users are not sufficiently involved in the process of development and testing [21,22]. With this final issue in mind, in the present study we interviewed individuals with a visual impairment with the aim to understand their experiences in hotel environments—a situation in which SSDs may be particularly useful.

Hotel stays may be suited for SSDs because (a) hotels are unfamiliar environments to most people and moving around in unfamiliar environments is a well-known challenge for individuals with a visual impairment [23,24], (b) a substantial number of perception-action tasks that are similar to the ones that have been addressed in laboratories with distance-to-vibration SSDs are performed in hotels (e.g., locomotion, obstacle avoidance, detecting apertures, grasping objects), (c) hotel environments show a moderate level of dynamism, unpredictability, and potential danger, and (d) SSDs that couple detected distance to vibration frequently use infrared sensors that work more reliably in indoor as compared to outdoor environments. In addition, investigating the experiences of individuals with a visual impairment in hotel environments is an important research topic in itself, allowing one to determine and improve the standards for the safety, comfort, and autonomy of the individuals [25].

We addressed the following research questions. First, what are the navigation and orientation challenges that individuals with a visual impairment encounter in the hotel environment? Second, of those challenges, which ones could potentially be overcome with appropriately

designed distance-to-vibration SSDs? And third, what is the knowledge and opinion of individuals with a visual impairment about electronic mobility aids in general and about distance-to-vibration SSDs in particular? To answer these questions, semi-structured interviews were conducted with eight individuals.

Method

Participants

A total of eight legally blind individuals participated in the study. According to the Spanish standards, being legally blind means that, for their stronger eye, the visual acuity was at most 10% and/or the visual field was at most 10deg [26]. Participants were included in the study only if they had travelled to different hotels in the last 6 years. Participants were recruited until a saturation point was reached [i.e., no new themes emerged in the data; 27]. All participants were Spanish. None of them had co-occurring disabilities. Table 1 provides further information about the participants.

The local ethics committee approved the research project (UAM-CEI-125-2563). Participants were recruited through the Fundación ONCE (Madrid, Spain), which is a large foundation that provides rehabilitation services. To obtain informed consent, the standard procedures of the Fundación ONCE were followed. As also recommended by Wittich et al. [28], this implies flexibility to accommodate individual needs. An accessible document with a description of the study was sent to participants by email. As a first way to provide informed consent, participants could sign and return the document or reply to the email. Additionally, verbal consent of all participants was recorded in audio-video format before the beginning of the interviews. The interview transcriptions are available on request.

Procedure

The interviews were conducted in online meetings with the individual participants. The platform Microsoft Teams was used, which was considered a convenient

Table 1. Participant information.

Participant number	Gender	Age	Type of blindness
P1	Male	32	Congenital
P2	Male	33	Congenital
P3	Female	67	Congenital
P4	Male	34	Acquired
P5	Female	43	Acquired
P6	Male	37	Acquired
P7	Female	33	Congenital
P8	Male	40	Congenital

and accessible option for all participants. The interviews were recorded in audio-video format for later analysis. Seven of them were conducted in Spanish by the second author, who is a native Spanish speaker, and the remaining one was conducted in English by the first author. The first and second authors were present during all interviews. None of the authors had a prior relation with the participating individuals. The interviews lasted between 45 and 60 min. None of the interviews were reconducted. The interview guide (see [Appendix A](#)) focused on general issues concerning hotel stays (Questions 1 to 3), challenges in the hotel environments (Questions 4 to 7), and technological aids (Questions 8 and 9).

Data coding

The criteria for reporting qualitative research by Tong et al. [29] were followed. The interviews were transcribed using the software Cockatoo and reviewed by a native Spanish speaker. Subsequently, the interviews were translated into English making use of Cockatoo, Google Translator, and DeepL. The data were organized and coded with Atlas.ti (Version 23.2.1) and analyzed through thematic analysis [30]. The thematic analysis comprised the following steps:

1. To get familiarized with the data, the interviews were read a minimum of three times.
2. The textual corpus was divided into verbatims.
3. An initial set of data codes was generated by labelling all verbatims that were relevant to the research questions.
4. An early thematic map was developed. The theme development involved examining the codes and relevant verbatims. The codes were clustered into meaningful patterns to generate subthemes, which were later combined into main themes.
5. To validate the analysis, identify gaps, evaluate the reliability, and reduce bias, an external judge was asked to code the verbatims using the list of codes that was generated during the previous steps.
6. After the coding that was performed by the external judge, two new codes were added to the previously generated ones.

Steps 1 to 3 were performed mainly by the first author, Steps 4 and 6 by the first and last author, and Step 5 by an external judge with experience in the field of qualitative analysis. The first author and the external judge also determined the valence (positive

or negative) for all verbatims about technological aids, because these aids were the main focus of the study. The external judge received an economic compensation for his contribution to the analysis.

Results

The textual corpus included 209 verbatims, which were categorized with 49 codes. All codes can be found in [Appendix B](#), together with verbatims that illustrate the codes. Three major themes were identified regarding the content of the verbatims: (1) navigation and orientation (subthemes: challenges and strategies), (2) wayfinding aids (subthemes: non-technological and technological aids), and (3) user needs (subthemes: autonomy, control over environment, and sociability). The first two themes were aligned with the interview guide. The third theme (user needs) emerged in a less expected way out of the data themselves. The frequencies and percentages of the verbatims per theme and subtheme can be found in [Table 2](#). An entity diagram of the themes and subthemes is provided in [Figure 1](#). To estimate the interrater agreement in the coding of the verbatims, Cohen's Kappa (κ) was determined for each subtheme. The interrater agreement was high (all κ s > .87). In the following sections, we describe the themes with exemplary verbatims. These descriptions are followed by a conceptual map that synthesizes the findings. Even though, in a strict sense, contingency tables and associated χ^2 analyses are not qualitative analyses, on occasions we also report these to complement the thematic findings.

Navigation and orientation

The theme of navigation and orientation refers to participants' actions for moving in the hotel environment. It included two subthemes: the challenges that are

Table 2. Frequencies and percentages of verbatims per theme and subtheme.

Themes	Verbatims	
	<i>n</i>	% ^a
Navigation and orientation	66	31.58
<i>Challenges</i>	46	22.01
<i>Strategies</i>	20	9.57
Wayfinding aids	76	36.36
<i>Non-technological</i>	21	10.05
<i>Technological</i>	55	26.32
User needs	67	32.06
<i>Autonomy</i>	33	15.79
<i>Control over environment</i>	18	8.61
<i>Sociability</i>	16	7.66

^aPercentages are calculated from the total number of verbatims ($n=209$).

Figure 1. Diagram depicting major themes and subthemes.

faced by individuals with a visual impairment and the strategies that they adopt. The theme comprised 31.58% ($n=66$) of the total number of verbatims, of which 22.01% was related to the challenges ($n=46$) and 9.57% to the strategies ($n=20$).

Challenges

Participants faced navigation and orientation challenges mainly due to the attributes of spaces, such as accessibility, localization, spatial configuration, and obstacles. Less frequently, the challenges were due to the dependency on others. These aspects of the challenges are described in turn.

Accessibility. Participants expressed that accessible hotels are infrequent and difficult to find, “Oh! no, forget about it. If you look for that [accessibility], you will be left without a hotel” (P1). Some of them expressed disappointment with the accessibility of hotels, “Beyond a ramp, what is accessibility? A ramp? That’s all! ... besides a physical accessibility logo, there is nothing else” (P6). Other participants always inquired about accessibility because of personal difficulties with stairs, highlighting the importance of accessibility information, “I ask everything about the space before going, because some places have many stairs, and I cannot go up ... so, for me it is a big problem, especially the stairs” (P5).

A critical factor concerning accessibility is the one of unexpected changes in ground level, “There is one point that is essential and that is to avoid unexpected

steps or ramps, in an unexpected place” (P2). Accessibility issues persisted in private spaces, such as when entering the room, because participants mentioned difficulties in using the key cards, “Another thing that seems silly, the key cards, many times you have to try those in four different ways to find the correct way to fit the key” (P7). Likewise, bathrooms were mentioned as inaccessible, “What you may find a little problematic, that has happened to us, is that some showers have a strange mechanism to open” (P1). One participant considered using bathtubs difficult and always asked about them before the hotel reservation, “I always ask about the bathroom, because if they have a bathtub instead of a shower, even with the bars, it is hard to use” (P5).

Localization. Participants reported different challenges with respect to global and local localization. With global localization we refer to determining the position of large-scale spaces and objects within the hotel building (e.g., the reception and hallways), and with local localization we refer to finding small objects within these larger spaces (e.g., elevator control panels). Concerning global localization, participants mentioned hotel entrances, “This hotel was one of a kind. You walked in and went down some stairs, and on the other side, there was a ramp that took you straight to the first floor. You could also enter through the ramp. So, it was weird, honestly, until we realized that the reception was downstairs. We went back out to the street and still couldn’t find it, until someone told us it was below the

ground level" (P1). Also mentioned were bathrooms, "I think that sometimes ... it is not clear where the bathrooms are" (P4), and elevators, "Some elevator doors are poorly positioned, making it difficult to notice them. They are often recessed in corners, causing people to walk so you can easily miss them. It is especially a problem if you're following a wall or the edge of a floor, because the elevators are often on a little raised platform" (P1).

Concerning local localization, participants mentioned the following issues: elevator operating panels, "So, we went through all the floors of the hotel and never made it to the reception floor because the zero button was outside the operating panel" (P1); bathroom amenities, "Last time we were in a hotel and there was no soap dish, it was attached to the wall in a corner. So, sometimes it is hard for you to deal with those things ... we consider finding the towels, the toilet paper, difficult, because sometimes they don't put it where they should put it" (P1); remote controls (of the television), "If you have to find the controller, only God knows where they decided to put it, another standard ... well, of course, it would be on a table. Because you will always look for it there. But if someone put it in the middle of a cute desk in the middle of the room, you probably won't find it" (P6); and, most particularly, electrical outlets, "You look for possible outlets to charge your cell phone ... you cannot find an outlet because they have decided to place it three meters from the bedside table. You can't find it because you're not going to move three meters from the table ... the logical thing would be for the sockets and lights to be close to the tables" (P6).

Spatial configuration. Mentions about the overall shape of a space or the arrangement of elements within a space were labelled as spatial configuration. Participants mentioned structural layouts (size, shape, and orientation), circulation pathways (corridors), vertical circulation (stairs, elevators, and ramps), and functional elements such as wayfinding signs. Confusion was expressed about the main halls of the hotels, "The issue arises with reception areas that have multiple corridors leading to a central hall that branches off to various points ... if you're not familiar with the layout, the star-shaped arrangement can be disorienting, at least on the first visit, right? Because you're walking along, thinking it is a square, and then suddenly you realize it is a pentagon" (P1). The size of spaces is considered to be an important aspect. Too narrow and too large spaces are both problematic, "When it [the hallway] is narrow, sometimes it is difficult to pass, because you have a dog and a suitcase" (P1), and, "What happens is that sometimes ... if the hall is very open and very spacious, maybe it is not so easy to find

... the problems usually arise when the hall is very spacious and does not have many references" (P6).

Sharing spaces with others may enhance the challenges due to spatial configurations. Finding bathrooms in shared spaces, for example, may be complex, "I remember walking through two changing rooms for two minutes and a glass door arrived. And then passing through hallways, and if benches on the floor change, if you don't take care, you'll hit them. Bathrooms are sometimes a bit complex" (P4). Participants added that signs can be helpful in finding and using different spaces, "I want the bathroom signs in braille, that's not going to happen" (P4). A shared space that was mentioned to be particularly difficult was the one of buffet services, "The buffet service, in the end, is a part that is very difficult to adapt, unless they give you something already pre-established, it is very difficult for a blind person to function in that type of environment" (P2).

Obstacles. An often-mentioned challenge was the one of obstacles (including inanimate objects as well as circulating people), such as columns and furniture, "Columns in open areas ... low tables ... a floor lamp" (P3), or decoration items, "The biggest problem in going to an Airbnb, a hotel, or a rented room, is often the excess of decoration or objects that are not very necessary but are there" (P4). In general, high obstacles were considered problematic, "I have been to a hotel where instead of having a lamp on the table, they had hanging spheres, and it was pretty awkward ... also it is not something that you usually have at home" (P2), and, "I usually don't like things over my face, the objects higher than my face, my chest or near my face, it is a pain for me, and I usually don't have closets or shelves like that [at home]. It's always okay when things are around my knees or under my knees, so, I can handle it, but if there is something in the room that is over my face or my head, it's like 'Oof! Oof!' I must be careful and need a lot of memory" (P5). As was the case with regard to spatial configurations, buffet settings were often mentioned with regard to obstacles, "I mean, there are people moving all the time, now you don't just depend on orienting yourself with respect to your table and where things are ... but it is a living space with more people, and you can't go there with a tray from one place to another" (P2).

Dependency on others. On occasions, participants mentioned their dependency on others (such as hotel staff and companions) to navigate and orient efficiently within the hotel environments. Help from hotel staff could be needed to get to the room the first time. In general, participants found the staff to be helpful. However, a few cases were described in which the

staff did not assist, "They usually accompany you, honestly. But it has happened to me sometimes that I had to ask, and they refused me because maybe there were a lot of people, or they didn't want to" (P7). One participant expressed frustration with situations in which the hotel staff was unavailable, "It feels like there's a total lack of understanding, no clear rules, and everything is just abnormal. Not only are there hotel rules to follow, but the building itself makes it hard to get around. But I know this isn't always the case, and they do sometimes walk you to your room. It is helpful for the first time, then you can find your way on your own" (P6).

Navigation and orientation challenges by type of space. To determine if specific challenges were associated with distinct types of spaces, a contingency table was computed (Table 3). For the ease of discussion, we categorized spaces into private (bedroom and bathroom) and public spaces (hotel entrance, hallways, elevators, and restaurant facilities). Whereas the overall number of challenges was similar for private and public spaces ($n=24$ and $n=22$, respectively), local localization challenges were more frequent in private spaces and spatial configuration challenges in public ones, $\chi^2(4, n=46) = 10.5, p = .032$.

Strategies

This subtheme concerns the strategies that were employed by participants for navigation and orientation in the hotel environments. Frequently mentioned strategies included: exploration, use of mental maps, reliance on environmental cues, and following spatial directions offered by others.

Exploration. Participants considered exploring their surroundings by themselves important, "First, I do an exploration round, well, where is this, where is that. And what's on the tables, that's it!" (P8). When participants travelled without a companion, a cautious and methodical exploration was used, "If you go alone, you have to do some exploration on your own, so, you go in an order, slowly because of course the sighted

person who designed the room doesn't think that a blind person will come to explore. So, you have to go slowly, carefully, because there could be a vase in the middle of nowhere, there could be a ceramic thing in the sink that looks really nice ... anything could happen. So, you have to go very slowly and recognize the places you find" (P6). Participants mentioned the effectiveness of the cane to identify obstacles during the exploration, "Mainly the low tables can be the most uncomfortable element ... I use the cane to explore" (P3). Limitations of the cane in detecting high level obstacles were also mentioned, "If something is high, it is not guaranteed that the cane will always detect it" (P3).

Mental maps. Mental maps involve internal representations of the environment's layout, including the positions of doors, furniture, and other landmarks. Mental maps are created at the time of arrival in order to facilitate navigation and orientation on subsequent occasions, "On first arrival, you do a tour and later you have already, let's say, done the tour in your head, and you already mentally know ... and then you can go on your own" (P1). Participants underscored the reliability of their mental maps, which help them navigate spaces once the routine is ingrained, "I explore, the table, where is the window, where is the door, where is the bathroom, what is the bathroom like inside, where is the toilet, where is the shower, where is everything. Sometimes twice. And then I can put my cane in one place and walk again a third time, trying to make the same path without missing. And it is like, 'Okay!' I'm safe. I know how everything is" (P5).

Environmental cues. In addition to mental maps, participants indicated the importance of cues from the surroundings, "Or maybe there is a ledge of something ... but for me, the maze type map, of going to the right, left, right, or go down seven steps, sometimes doesn't work ... then what I use is more references of space ... I'm associating it [the navigation] with things, for example, a change in floor mat" (P2). Auditory cues are also important for an efficient navigation and orientation, "There are two types of blind people, the person who needs sound depending on the noise the tip of the cane makes to get around and the person who interprets the echoes of the sound of talking or walking as it can give you information about how the sound wave is distributed. If I walk quickly, I know that I have walls to the right and to the left because I am making an echo sound and that gives me information about how much I can move" (P1). Participants indicated that auditory cues provide information about the layout of spaces, "Sound also gives a lot of information ... you can hear the room. When you enter, you can hear the spaciousness of the room" (P6).

Table 3. Contingency table for navigation and orientation challenges by type of space.

Challenges	Private space		Public space	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Accessibility	13	54.17 (1.21)	8	36.36 (-1.21)
Localization (Global)	1	4.17 (-0.67)	2	9.09 (0.67)
Localization (Local)	4	16.67 (2.01)*	–	0.00 (-2.01)*
Obstacles	6	25.00 (-0.51)	7	31.82 (0.51)
Spatial configuration	–	0.00 (-2.47)*	5	22.73 (2.47)*
Total	24	100	22	100

Note. Percentages are calculated from the totals per type of space. Adjusted standardized residuals are shown in parentheses.

*Values equal to or greater than ± 1.96 are significant ($p < .05$).

Spatial directions. A final strategy for navigation and orientation that was mentioned is the use of spatial directions offered by others. One participant mentioned, “When I reach, someone often guides a little. I have good spatial location in my head and if someone tells me three doors to the right hallway or to the left, I usually understand it well and can usually store it and practice” (P3).

Wayfinding aids

This theme concerns wayfinding aids and includes the subthemes non-technological aids and technological aids. The theme comprises 36.36% ($n=76$) of the verbatims. Of these, the non-technological aids subtheme made up 10.05% ($n=21$), and the technological one 26.32% ($n=55$).

Non-technological aids

The non-technological aids that were mentioned by participants were guide dogs and the white cane (hereafter, cane). The following subsections describe the benefits and challenges that were reported for these aids.

Guide dogs. The benefits of dogs are related to autonomy and a sense of security. Guide dogs often allow participants to move through complex environments more easily than a cane, “For me the best thing about the guide dog is that ... the dog is zigzagging, and I don’t know why. That doesn’t happen with the cane, in the end I’m going to move all the time as I don’t know what is in front of me. It is a much more fluid movement that you have with a dog. And I think that can be achieved with technology and with time” (P2). Dogs can also provide security by detecting obstacles at different heights, “I almost hit a scaffolding that was at the height of my head ... the cane doesn’t provide security, the cane came in and it was me there hitting my head, so what’s going to give you more security? In this case, a few eyes, the dog is going to push you back” (P2).

The challenges that were mentioned in relation to guide dogs concern maintenance, responsibility, and environmental limitations. Maintenance challenges include the financial burden, the need for regular care, and the responsibility of supporting a healthy lifestyle for the dog, “And I love dogs, I want a guide dog. But you also must be realistic that even financially, having a dog is an expense to take into account. And even if everything is very good, still, it is a fixed monthly expense. And well, it has a life, there are many things. And a responsibility too” (P2). Other challenges relate to the retirement of the dog and the attachment to it

as a living being, “When a dog retires, they [the individuals with a visual impairment] usually don’t want another one. It’s complicated” (P2).

Cane. The benefits of the cane include its utility for navigation in public and narrow spaces, where dogs might struggle, “You think that with a dog and a suitcase, there are three people. One [the dog] on the left and the suitcase on the right. When you go with a cane it is reduced to one ... if I have to go to the subway which is 400 meters away, I’m not going with the dog ... I go with the cane” (P1). The cane was also mentioned with regard to exploration, for example of the room, “The cane helps a lot to get around the room. Once you go through it and know what it is like, you go much faster and better because you have learned it, as it is a small space” (P6). A disadvantage of the cane is the fact that it has a limited range. Obstacles that are not covered by the sweeping movements are typically missed. High obstacles are often problematic, “Well it doesn’t give me security because the cane will be able to tell you what is in front of you, on the floor, but what you have in front of your waist or above, it is never going to tell you” (P1).

Technological aids

The second subtheme of the wayfinding aids is the one of technological aids. This subtheme includes SSDs, scanning apps, and video calls. Note that we use the abbreviation app to refer to smartphone applications. Before we turn to these specific aids, more general remarks on technological aids are presented.

General remarks. Without mentioning specific aids, participants generally considered technological advances useful, “Everything helps. There is nothing that is useless” (P3). Some participants expected future developments on hand-held devices for obstacle detection, “I think that with all the technology we have there should be a kind of sensor directly attached to the hands or something that you have to carry in your hand like a micro camera, so as you move forward, it indicates a clear path and detects obstacle to the right, obstacle to the left and gives you a lot of auditory information” (P2). Another participant expected future developments on glasses that allow the detection of high obstacles, “This is the future ... having a pair of glasses that you put on, it analyzes you, it tracks everything, it warns you about the high-level obstacles or whatever you want” (P7). Also mentioned was the expectation of more detailed object identification, “In fact, one of the things that can be very good in interiors, precisely relying on artificial intelligence that is already recognizing so many things in the

environment. If we can reach the level of precise details where it can tell you 'Table with four chairs and a flowerpot in the middle' when you are looking at the photo of a table ... the keys ... or, for example, as I was finding my earphone capsules this morning" (P4).

Although participants were often positive about potential future achievements, they frequently expressed disappointments with actual devices. The lack of the involvement of end-users in the design of aids was mentioned as a limiting factor, "Well, designing and inventing things without taking into account for who you invent is a bit complicated" (P2). Other limiting factors that were mentioned were weight, having multiple components, insufficient obstacle recognition, and incompatibility with social concerns, "Another problem is that many of these products are very bulky, you have glasses with a cable, then you have a device in your pocket. Devices like glasses that do not have these types of problems, they are even limited to recognizing certain types of obstacles ... or one that was a helmet ... it's not practical ... also combine it with your social life" (P2). As another critical observation, one participant expressed a concern for too much dependence on smartphones, "I don't want to cook with an app ... I don't want to depend on a cell phone for everything" (P7). It was also argued that, rather than replacing the cane, aids should complement the cane, "They [designers of technological aids] say that 'The cane is not good enough, let's invent something that must replace the cane', and I don't know if you are going to invent something that will replace the cane, you must also think of a complement" (P2).

SSDs. Some participants had tested SSDs, although none of them were regular users of such devices. Four types were mentioned. One of them was a cane that provides vibrotactile information, "It vibrated depending on whether an obstacle is approached" (P1). A disadvantage of the device was the difficulty to "lean toward anything" (P1) while using the device, because this would cause the device to vibrate.

Another vibrotactile SSD that had been tested was a wristband with vibrotactile information (the Sunu Band), "It has a sonar sensor that vibrates when it detects obstacles" (P1). The participant believed that the device was useful for individuals with a recent visual impairment more than for others, "I suppose that for a blind person who has recently gone blind, who moves very slowly or who needs another type of security in terms of space, there are these things that can either facilitate or give the feeling of greater security. But for a person who has mobility, well come on,

who is functioning well, who is already used to it, I think they don't need it much" (P1). The lack of a precise control over the sensor on certain occasions was mentioned as a disadvantage, "I find the bracelet inconvenient, taking into account that you can carry a bag in your hand, which you are moving in your hand, so, you do not have exact control of where you are focusing with the sensor of the bracelet, and many times the bracelet is vibrating ... and I don't know why it is vibrating" (P1).

The third SSD that had been tested consisted of glasses with auditory information. As positive features of this device it was indicated that the device was lightweight and inexpensive, "A camera mounted on glasses, which depending on sounds, gives you information about obstacles and one of its interesting contributions was that it was very light ... and was not very expensive, but it still needs improvement" (P3). The device, however, failed in outdoor environments, "The truth is that the street test did not give very good results" (P3).

The final SSD that had been tested also used auditory information, this time as an additional feature of a cane. The device was appreciated for its potential utility in open spaces, "You put a remote control on the top and wear headphones. I think that can be very interesting in open spaces, such as fields, open towns, and so on" (P3). Even so, the participant had tested the device only in crowded streets, which led to an overload of information, "In Madrid, with a lot of people, there were so many obstacles, and it was constantly beeping, and in the end, you get dizzy ... and discriminating is very difficult ... I haven't tried it there [in open spaces]. I have tried it in Madrid city, and it really didn't solve much for me" (P3). Another participant mentioned financial concerns with regard to a cane with auditory information, "But it [the cane] is expensive in most situations ... I think this is the most important problem" (P5).

Scanning apps. Several scanning apps and devices were mentioned. Positive features were indicated for the app Seeing AI, "On the one hand, it has real-time text recognition, it has a light detector, basically it will focus with the mobile camera and verbalize the text to you in real time ... and then the light detector to, well, avoid leaving lights on" (P2). The app Yuka was considered helpful for fast scanning, "The app is designed to scan products and tell you about the health of food, but I use it a lot to find products because it has a very fast scan ... as many times it detects very quickly" (P2). Another device allows users to record descriptions of different items, which are

recognized with specific labels. One participant used this device for a personalized inventory of spices, with the voices of friends, "It's a voice recorder as they say, it is a flash drive with a miniature speaker and a label of chickpea size can be stuck on a spice jar, so, when you turn on the machine and press the record button, you describe it. I brought my colleagues home, and I have spices with all the voices of my friends" (P4). Also mentioned was the scanning device LEO (full name in Spanish: *Lector de Etiquetas ONCE*), "These are a kind of little pencils that come with some stickers that you can also put on washable and dirty clothes ... you can scan and record it with your voice" (P7). The same device was described by another participant as a "resource saver" (P6).

Among the disadvantages of scanning apps are difficulties related to the focusing direction of the phone, "[the app] tells you 'You have pointed!' and I don't know what, 'You have marked with your finger!' and I don't know how much, higher or lower" (P6). Additionally, these apps also require a phone of sufficient quality, "First, you must have a good cell phone, which I think is selective as it leaves people out. Second, it consumes the battery in no time" (P3). Social concerns are also relevant, "I am trying to find it with the NaviLens system, and I try not to disturb my surroundings, because if I am on my smartphone and my smartphone is talking all the time, people around me can get disturbed" (P5). Finally, one participant mentioned the low quality of free apps and financial concerns with better ones, "There is a good app to try to identify colors and that would be great for me in my wardrobe, but it doesn't work properly most of the time, and the good one is expensive" (P5).

Video calls. Participants mentioned the video calling app Be My Eyes. This app allows individuals with a visual impairment to get assistance from sighted individuals. On one occasion, a participant was not able to identify a clothes valet stand, "And I didn't know what it was ... my head was exploding ... no matter how much I tried, I couldn't think of what it could be. And I made a video call, and he [the sighted individual] told me that is for the suits" (P8). On another occasion, the participant used the app to localize electrical outlets in the hotel room, "I made a video call to see exactly if there are more electrical outlets" (P8).

Affective evaluation of technological aids. To determine whether technological aids were perceived positively or negatively, a valence analysis was performed. The valence of each verbatim was determined by the first author and an external judge. The interrater agreement was high ($\kappa=0.82$; $SE=0.07$). The here-reported analysis

concerns the types of aids with most verbatims (SSDs and scanning apps). A significant association was observed between valence and type of aid, $\chi^2(1, n=29) = 3.99, p = .046$. As can be seen in Table 4, SSDs were considered mainly in a negative way, whereas scanning apps were mentioned in positive and negative ways in almost equal proportions.

User needs

This theme describes the user needs that were expressed by participants in relation to the hotel stays. The theme comprised 32.06% ($n=67$) of the verbatims. Three subthemes were obtained: autonomy (15.79%; $n=33$), control over the environment (8.61%; $n=18$), and sociability (7.66%; $n=16$).

Autonomy

With autonomy we refer to a sense of independence in travelling and accomplishing tasks. The subtheme includes verbatims related to the need of help from others, the capacity to understand the environment, and the possibility to explore the environment.

Participants frequently expressed a lack of autonomy, "I, personally, like to go for vacations, but to go sightseeing on my own is risky and I consider that I do not have the capacity to do so and therefore I do not do it. I am not going alone" (P3), or, "On vacation I normally go accompanied, because I understand that for a blind person, going on vacation is not their strength" (P6). Even when travelling alone, help from others is often necessary, "No matter how much one manages and how much he is autonomous, there is one thing about new places and that even if you don't go with someone, in the end you have to ask" (P1). Help from others facilitates, among other things, the understanding of the environment, "If I go alone, who will tell me the surroundings?" (P3).

Participants expressed the belief that, on occasions, sighted individuals do not sufficiently allow or promote autonomy. One participant said, "Rehabilitation technicians ... do not give the autonomy that they have to give ... they do not give them [the individuals with a visual impairment] the orientation 'Go to the

Table 4. Contingency table for valence by technological aids.

Valence	SSD		Scanning app	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Negative	10	90.91 (1.99)*	10	55.56 (-1.99)*
Positive	1	9.09 (-1.99)*	8	44.44 (1.99)*
Total	11	100	18	100

Note. Percentages are calculated from the totals per type of aid. Adjusted standardized residuals are shown in parentheses.

*Values equal to or greater than ± 1.96 are significant ($p < .05$).

right and see what you find'. What if maybe the best way for me is to hit three terraces? And maybe I say 'Ah, okay, well now I know that after the terrace I turn right, and I won't hit it again' ... in the desire to protect, they are unintentionally ruining the sixth sense that a disabled person can have" (P2). Likewise, the desire of sighted individuals to protect may limit the opportunities to explore, "When my mother came to accompany me to a place, she said 'No, it's quieter on the right', but I want to go on the left and [I asked her to] tell me what I have on the left and if you don't tell me anything ... I'll hit it and I'll see" (P1).

Exploration helps individuals with a visual impairment to understand the environment, and it thereby makes autonomous navigation easier. Typically, after getting in a hotel room, the first thing that participants do is to explore, "I explore it a little, I find where the bathroom is, where the TV is, if there is a dresser, if there is a window, if there is a balcony, if there is such a thing ... especially the issue of plugs, what I look for the most is if there are any [plugs] in the room, how many there are, where they are in the bathroom" (P7).

Control over the environment

The subtheme of control over the environment includes verbatims about the efficient interaction with and management of the environment. Being organized was found to be crucial to individuals with a visual impairment, "[I] keep track of everything of what's in my environment. Or what I can control ... if you're with another blind person ... tell them where you have your things. The other person should do the same. And try to keep things as organized as possible so as not to lose them" (P8). The importance of a careful organization was also emphasized by other participants, "Once we arrive in the room, where we will be sleeping ... I have already decided what my room is going to be, my space, where I can leave my things. And I am very rigorous when it comes to organizing my things, well, the backpack goes to the closet that corresponds to me, so, here is my backpack, cell phone charger in this socket, headphones on the bedside table, a bottle of water on the bedside table, a package of Kleenex" (P4). As a further illustration of the importance of a careful organization, one participant expressed a preference for small and closed storage spaces, "If the bedside table has a drawer, for me it's wonderful. It is a closed, limited environment, which I can then check very well before I leave. And I'm not going to leave anything behind because nothing is going to fall from there" (P6).

Sociability

With sociability we refer to the enjoyment of social interactions with other living beings, humans as well as animals, and the possibility of social support. In general, participants indicated that they liked to travel with a companion, "It [travelling with a companion] is more fun" (P8). They also expressed that social support makes travelling easier, "Logically, when you go with someone who can see or who at least has some functional eyesight, things become much easier" (P1), or, "I also consider that this [having a travel companion] is not essential, but it can make your trip easier and simpler" (P7). The need of help from others, however, is also a form of dependency, "What is no longer the same is that you can ask someone on the street for help, which is another possible solution, but you don't always have someone who can help you. So, this is already a dependency" (P3). A type of social support can also be provided by guide dogs, "Well, there are many factors. It [the guide dog] is a responsibility, it is also about money ... but in the end, inevitably, it is also a buddy" (P7).

User needs by type of space

Overall, participants mentioned slightly more needs in private spaces ($n=25$) than in public ones ($n=21$). To test if there is a relation between user needs and type of space, a chi-square test was performed. This test indicated that the association between needs and spaces was indeed significant, $\chi^2(4, n=46) = 27.5, p < .001$ (Table 5). In private spaces, higher frequencies were observed for autonomy through exploration and control over the environment. In public spaces, higher frequencies were observed for autonomy through others and sociability.

Conceptual thematic map

Figure 2 presents a thematic map with the most relevant relations that were observed in the data. Non-technological aids allow individuals with a visual impairment to experience a dynamic flow of movement (guide dogs), overcome obstacles (guide dogs and cane), and explore the environment (cane). Non-technological aids also have limitations, primary among which are the detection of high and distant obstacles with the cane. Guide dogs contribute to the satisfaction of all three user needs. The cane, on the other hand, provides autonomy, but is more limited in providing control. Of the technological aids, we focused on SSDs, which come with their own set of benefits and challenges. The SSDs that had been

tested by participants allowed the detection of obstacles under some circumstances (e.g., in not too crowded environments), but were not used to overcome obstacles. Additionally, participants reported information overload and a lack of precision with SSDs. Regarding user needs, SSDs were on occasions highlighted as potentially beneficial tools for promoting autonomy and control, because they may provide users with information that aids in navigating the surroundings more effectively.

Discussion

For SSDs to be effective, they must be adapted to potential users. This study therefore explored the navigation and orientation challenges of individuals with

a visual impairment, in the particular case of hotel stays. The findings highlight that the challenges are substantial, including issues with accessibility, localization, spatial configurations, and obstacles. The high levels of difficulty of navigation and orientation that were mentioned are in line with the results of studies about the challenges of individuals with a visual impairment in more general tourist environments [31] and in indoor settings [32; cf. 33]. In hotel environments, the challenges are often enhanced by the complex and unique design features of the spaces. Generally, participants considered that hotels are not designed for individuals with a visual impairment.

Challenges in the hotel environment

The challenges differed between public and private spaces within the hotels. More challenges related to spatial configurations were mentioned for public spaces, and more challenges related to localization for private ones. The challenges regarding spatial configurations included changes in ground level, obstacles that are very low, obstacles that are at the height of the body or head, and the shape of hallways that are too large to be explored with the cane, such as a typical entrance hall of a hotel. Spatial configurations that change from one occasion to the next, such as the position of tables in restaurants, were also mentioned to be complicated. Several of these findings are in line with previous research [23], and they may be

Table 5. Contingency table for user needs by type of space.

User needs	Private space		Public space	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Autonomy				
<i>Through others</i>	1	4.00 (-3.72)*	11	52.38 (3.72)*
<i>Through understanding the environment</i>	3	12.00 (0.27)	2	9.52 (-0.27)
<i>Through exploration</i>	6	24.00 (2.41)*	–	0.00 (-2.41)*
Control over environment	13	52.00 (3.47)*	1	4.76 (-3.47)*
Sociability	2	8.00 (-2.16)*	7	33.33 (2.16)*
Total	25	100	21	100

Note. Percentages are calculated from the totals per type of space. Adjusted standardized residuals are shown in parentheses. *Values equal to or greater than ± 1.96 are significant ($p < .05$).

Figure 2. Conceptual thematic map illustrating how wayfinding aids (middle) are related to aspects of navigation and orientation (left) and user needs (right). Green arrows indicate facilitation, and red arrows indicate difficulties in overcoming the challenge, using the strategy, or fulfilling the need.

connected to laboratory research that demonstrates that SSDs have the potential to assist with the detection of ground-level obstacles [15,34] and medium-high obstacles [14]. The finding that spaces that are too large to be explored with a cane are considered problematic may also have design implications. This is so because the designers of SSDs can, to some degree, choose the range of sensitivity of the to-be-designed devices, and hence adapt that range to the size of the spaces that are most challenging to the users.

The localization challenges that were mentioned for private spaces included finding electrical outlets and remote controls. Another often-mentioned challenge was entering the hotel room with a keycard, which typically provides only visual cues concerning its orientation. The solution to such challenges should be sought in advanced scanning apps or in more user-friendly designs [25]. Problems with electrical outlets, for example, could be reduced by the standardization of the locations of the outlets. Likewise, a haptic cue on keycards that breaks the symmetry would be a relatively simple and effective improvement.

To overcome navigation and orientation challenges, individuals with a visual impairment employ several strategies. Importantly among these, exploration was often mentioned as a way to come to understand the surroundings. Developing mental maps, the use of environmental cues, and asking for spatial directions were also mentioned. As do Jeamwathanachai et al. [32], we believe that the use of a combination of strategies provides most confidence to individuals with a visual impairment. The frequent mention of exploration as a strategy might be related to previous studies with SSDs, because these studies emphasized the usefulness of active exploration [17,34]. The use of environmental cues may also be relevant to researchers interested in SSDs, because SSDs may be designed to enhance the detection of the type of cues that individuals with a visual impairment are interested in.

Non-technological and technological aids

In terms of non-technological aids, participants referred to the white cane, which is effective for the detection of obstacles in the area that is covered with the sweeping movements, and guide dogs, which are valued for their ability to navigate in a zigzag pattern around obstacles. Similar observations can be found in Williams et al. [35]: Whereas the cane is used to explore, a guide dog anticipates the environment. In agreement with such results, some individuals with a visual impairment prefer a guide dog over a cane

because the dog guides them toward the free space without having to bother about the location of obstacles. This is an interesting observation for the design of SSDs. Most SSDs indicate where obstacles are. However, it is also possible to design SSDs that indicate where the free (or walkable) space is. The remarks by the dog users in our study indicate that this latter possibility may be a worthwhile alternative. In addition, Williams et al. noted that whether individuals are predominantly cane users or dog users affects their approach to navigation, which, in turn, may affect which type of technological aid is most useful to them.

Regarding technological aids, participants mentioned SSDs, scanning apps, and video calls. From our analysis on the affective evaluation of the aids, one can conclude that scanning apps were described in positive and negative ways in about equal proportions. However, SSDs were mainly described in a negative way. Only a few SSDs had actually been tested by our participants. A lack of precision and sensory overload were mentioned as negative aspects for these devices, which is in line with previous research [22,35; cf. 36]. For one of the SSDs, difficulties with the control of the direction of focusing were mentioned. This example may illustrate that, in addition to more user-centered designs, efficient training programs are needed [1,18,19]. Although participants mostly had a negative opinion about the SSDs that they had tried, they were typically positive about the potential that SSDs hold for the future.

SSDs and human needs

Another substantial finding that emerged from this study relates to the user needs for autonomy, control, and sociability, highlighting a gap often overlooked in research on SSDs. While previous studies have primarily focused on SSDs as tools for autonomy and mobility [19,37], few have considered their role in facilitating social interactions. Issues related to social engagement were repeatedly mentioned in the interviews. Examples of these are the appreciation that individuals expressed for an app that connects users with a visual impairment to sighted volunteers, and the descriptions of guide dogs as a source of social support [cf. 38]. It may also be relevant in this regard to note that Packer et al. [31] performed their study in the context of focus groups, which is one of the ways that can be used to strengthen the social dimension of research on SSDs.

The findings discussed in the previous paragraph can be related to the self-determination theory that was proposed by Deci and Ryan [39]. According to that theory, sociability (referred to by the authors as *relatedness*)

is an innate and universal human need, alongside the needs for autonomy and competence. The degree of satisfaction of these needs is related to well-being [40]. Remember that these three needs were all observed in our data. To achieve intrinsically motivated behavior, which is a self-rewarding behavior, the context should support the satisfaction of these needs. The fact that SSDs are not frequently used in everyday life situations may therefore indicate that the potential users do not believe (or are not aware) that SSDs allow the satisfaction of their basic needs. This is a relevant observation for the field of sensory substitution. It is commonly understood that the field needs engineers that design robust and cost-efficient devices, experts in user experience that evaluate the opinions of individuals about the devices, psychologists that study how individuals actively perceive with the devices, and experts in training that understand how individuals may efficiently learn to use the novel stimulation that is provided. The broadest implication of the current results, we believe, is that the field also needs social psychologists that understand which factors lead individuals with a visual impairment to be intrinsically motivated to use SSDs, which is to say, the factors that lead to the satisfaction of basic needs and to the awareness of users that the devices satisfy these needs.

Conclusions and recommendations

Let us conclude by listing the recommendations for the field of sensory substitution that can be based on our research: (a) SSDs should provide precise information that is relevant to issues that are challenging to users, such as hanging obstacles, low obstacles, and changes in ground level, (b) one should minimize information overload, for example by enabling mode selection based on context, such as obstacle-detection in open spaces or open-space-detection in cluttered ones, (c) one should carefully think about the range of sensitivity of SSDs, making them most useful for distances that are most problematic to users, such as the typical size of the entrance halls of hotels, (d) SSDs should be aesthetically appealing, lightweight, robust, and affordable, (e) the end-users should be involved at early phases of the design and research process, (f) protocols for training the use of SSDs should be developed, (g) features that facilitate social interaction should be considered, and (h) the field as a whole should carefully think about how SSDs may facilitate the satisfactions of the needs of individuals with a visual impairment, because need satisfaction is the basic ingredient of the motivation to use the devices

in everyday-life situations, as well as being a basic ingredient of high levels of well-being.

Acknowledgements

We thank all participants for their time and Néstor Cano Díaz for his help with the coding process.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 956003.

Notes on contributors

Saroosh Bilal is pursuing a PhD in Psychology at the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid with the support of a Marie Curie scholarship. She holds a master's degree in biomedical sciences, with research emphasis on rehabilitation technology, and a bachelor's degree in orthotics and prosthetics. With a multidisciplinary background, her research aims to bridge the fields of psychology, rehabilitation, and movement science. Her research, inspired by ecological psychology, investigates the understanding of perception-action coupling, perceptual learning, and user-centric design to enhance the utility of sensory substitution devices.

Jorge Rebate holds a bachelor's degree in communication sciences from the Universidad Rey Juan Carlos in Madrid, specializing in advertising and public relations (2011–2015). He later completed a master's degree in user-centered design at the Universidad de la Rioja (2018–2019), presenting a master's thesis that proposed an accessibility evaluation in video games focused on challenges related to manipulation and manual dexterity. Currently, he works at Fundación ONCE, applying the user-centered design methodology in cutting-edge innovation projects, including fields such as robotics and artificial intelligence, where accessibility and inclusion are essential requirements. Additionally, he tutors master's theses and has been a lecturer for the course *User Requirements: Research and Analysis* at the Universidad Oberta de Catalunya since 2022.

David M. Jacobs, PhD, is associate professor and co-director of the Perception and Action Research Group at the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. Before coming to Madrid in 2007, he worked as a temporary teacher/researcher at the Université d'Aix-Marseille and as a post-doctoral fellow at the University of Connecticut. His main theoretical contributions are formulated around an ecological theory of learning that he, with Claire F. Michaels, has named direct learning. His most recent empirical research aims to apply and advance ecological ideas about perception, action, and learning, in the fields of sensory substitution, aviation, and sports.

Verónica Sevillano, PhD, is associate professor of environmental and social psychology at the Facultad de Psicología of the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. She has been a Fulbright scholar at Princeton University. She is currently a board member of the Spanish Environmental Psychology Association (PSICAMB). Working with Susan T. Fiske, she developed the Stereotype Content Model applied to Animals. Her research examines people-environment relations and social stereotypes of animals.

ORCID

Saroosh Bilal <http://orcid.org/0009-0000-0193-2449>
 Jorge Rebate <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-2627-6649>
 David M. Jacobs <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-2954-5293>
 Verónica Sevillano <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-9285-4035>

References

- [1] Ptito M, Bleau M, Djerourou I, et al. Brain-machine interfaces to assist the blind. *Front Hum Neurosci.* 2021;15:638887. doi:10.3389/fnhum.2021.638887.
- [2] Bach-y-Rita P, Collins CC, Saunders FA, et al. Vision substitution by tactile image projection. *Nature.* 1969;221(5184):963–964. doi:10.1038/221963a0.
- [3] Chebat DR, Harrar V, Kupers R, et al. Sensory substitution and the neural correlates of navigation in blindness. In Pissaloux E, Velazquez R, editors. *Mobility of visually impaired people: fundamentals and ICT assistive technologies.* Cham: Springer; 2018. p. 167–200. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-54446-5_6.
- [4] Auvray M, Hanneton S, O'Regan JK. Learning to perceive with a visuo-auditory substitution system: localisation and object recognition with 'The Voice'. *Perception.* 2007;36(3):416–430. doi:10.1068/p5631.
- [5] Maidenbaum S, Hanassy S, Abboud S, et al. The "EyeCane", a new electronic travel aid for the blind: technology, behavior & swift learning. *Restor Neurol Neurosci.* 2014;32(6):813–824. doi:10.3233/RNN-130351.
- [6] Kolarik AJ, Timmis MA, Cirstea S, et al. Sensory substitution information informs locomotor adjustments when walking through apertures. *Exp Brain Res.* 2014;232(3):975–984. doi:10.1007/s00221-013-3809-5.
- [7] Nagel SK, Carl C, Kringe T, et al. Beyond sensory substitution: learning the sixth sense. *J Neural Eng.* 2005;2(4):R13–R26. doi:10.1088/1741-2560/2/4/R02.
- [8] Meijer PB. An experimental system for auditory image representations. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng.* 1992;39(2):112–121. doi:10.1109/10.121642.
- [9] Cancar L, Díaz A, Barrientos A, et al. Tactile-Sight: a sensory substitution device based on distance related vibrotactile flow. *Int J Adv Rob Syst.* 2013;10(6):272. doi:10.5772/56235.
- [10] Saleh M, Ibrahim A, Ansovin F, et al. Wearable system for sensory substitution for prosthetics. In *2018 New Generation of CAS (NGCAS).* Valeta, Malta: IEEE; 2018. p. 110–113. doi:10.1109/NGCAS.2018.8572173.
- [11] Kilian J, Neugebauer A, Scherffig L, et al. The unfolding space glove: a wearable spatio-visual to haptic sensory substitution device for blind people. *Sensors (Basel).* 2022;22(5):1859. doi:10.3390/s22051859.
- [12] Eagleman DM, Perrotta MV. The future of sensory substitution, addition, and expansion via haptic devices. *Front Hum Neurosci.* 2023;16:1055546. doi:10.3389/fnhum.2022.1055546.
- [13] Lobo L, Travieso D, Jacobs DM, et al. Sensory substitution: using a vibrotactile device to orient and walk to targets. *J Exp Psychol Appl.* 2018;24(1):108–124. doi:10.1037/xap0000154.
- [14] Lobo L, Nordbeck PC, Raja V, et al. Route selection and obstacle avoidance with a short-range haptic sensory substitution device. *Int J Hum Comput Stud.* 2019;132:25–33. doi:10.1016/j.ijhcs.2019.03.004.
- [15] Lobo L, Travieso D, Barrientos A, et al. Stepping on obstacles with a sensory substitution device on the lower leg: practice without vision is more beneficial than practice with vision. *PLoS One.* 2014;9(6):e98801. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0098801.
- [16] de Paz C, Travieso D, Ibáñez-Gijón J, et al. Sensory substitution: the affordance of passability, body-scaled perception, and exploratory movements. *PLoS One.* 2019;14(3):e0213342. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0213342.
- [17] de Paz C, Ibáñez-Gijón J, Travieso D, et al. Grasping objects with a sensory substitution glove. *Int J Hum Comput Stud.* 2023;170:102963. doi:10.1016/j.ijhcs.2022.102963.
- [18] Bilal S, Bongers RM, Jacobs DM. Reaching and grasping with a sensory substitution glove: variability of practice effects. *J Motor Learn Dev.* 2025:1–23. doi:10.1123/jmld.2024-0060.
- [19] Elli GV, Benetti S, Collignon O. Is there a future for sensory substitution outside academic laboratories? *Multisens Res.* 2014;27(5–6):271–291. doi:10.1163/22134808-00002460.
- [20] Martiniello N, Eisenbarth W, Lehane C, et al. Exploring the use of smartphones and tablets among people with visual impairments: are mainstream devices replacing the use of traditional visual aids? *Assist Technol.* 2022;34(1):34–45. doi:10.1080/10400435.2019.1682084.
- [21] Hoffmann R, Spagnol S, Kristjánsson Á, et al. Evaluation of an audio-haptic sensory substitution device for enhancing spatial awareness for the visually impaired. *Optom Vis Sci.* 2018;95(9):757–765. doi:10.1097/OPX.0000000000001284.
- [22] Real S, Araujo A. Navigation systems for the blind and visually impaired: past work, challenges, and open problems. *Sensors (Basel).* 2019;19(15):3404. doi:10.3390/s19153404.
- [23] Goldschmidt M. Orientation and mobility training to people with visual impairments. In Pissaloux E, Velázquez R, editors. *Mobility of visually impaired people: fundamentals and ICT assistive technologies.* Cham, Switzerland: Springer; 2018. p. 237–262. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-54446-5_8.
- [24] Wu YH, Martiniello N, Swenor BK. Building a more accessible conference for researchers with vision impairment. *JAMA Ophthalmol.* 2022;140(2):113–114. doi:10.1001/jamaophthalmol.2021.5613.
- [25] Tutuncu O, Lieberman L. Accessibility of hotels for people with visual impairments: from research to prac-

- tice. *J Vis Impair Blind*. 2016;110(3):163–175. doi:10.1177/0145482X1611000303.
- [26] Bron AM, Viswanathan AC, Thelen U, et al. International vision requirements for driver licensing and disability pensions: using a milestone approach in characterization of progressive eye disease. *Clin Ophthalmol*. 2010;4:1361–1369. doi:10.2147/OPTH.S15359.
- [27] Denscombe M. *The good research guide: for small-scale social research projects*. London, England: McGraw-Hill Educativo; 2017.
- [28] Wittich W, Boie NR, Jaiswal A. Methodological approaches to obtaining informed consent when conducting research with individuals with deafblindness. *Int J Qual Methods*. 2023;22:1–11. doi:10.1177/16094069231205176.
- [29] Tong A, Sainsbury P, Craig J. Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ): a 32-item checklist for interviews and focus groups. *Int J Qual Health Care*. 2007;19(6):349–357. doi:10.1093/intqhc/mzm042.
- [30] Braun V, Clarke V. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual Res Psychol*. 2006;3(2):77–101. doi:10.1191/1478088706qp063oa.
- [31] Packer TL, Small J, Darcy S. *Tourist experiences of individuals with vision impairment*. Gold Coast, Australia: Sustainable Tourism CRC; 2008.
- [32] Jeamwathanachai W, Wald M, Wills G. Indoor navigation by blind people: behaviors and challenges in unfamiliar spaces and buildings. *Br J Vis Impair*. 2019;37(2):140–153. doi:10.1177/0264619619833723.
- [33] Rizzo JR, Rosenblum P, Samuel C, et al. Accessible scientific conferences for blind and low vision professionals and researchers: a necessary step for achieving STEM equity. *Disabil Soc*. 2024;1–7. doi:10.1080/09687599.2024.2412269.
- [34] Díaz A, Barrientos A, Jacobs DM, et al. Action-contingent vibrotactile flow facilitates the detection of ground level obstacles with a partly virtual sensory substitution device. *Hum Mov Sci*. 2012;31(6):1571–1584. doi:10.1016/j.humov.2012.05.006.
- [35] Williams MA, Hurst A, Kane SK. "Pray before you step out": describing personal and situational blind navigation behaviors. In *Proceedings of the 15th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility*; 2013. pp. 1–8. doi:10.1145/2513383.2513449.
- [36] Loomis JM, Klatzky RL, Giudice NA. Sensory substitution of vision: importance of perceptual and cognitive processing. In Manduchi R, Kurniawan S, editors. *Assistive technology for blindness and low vision*. Boca Raton, Florida: CRC Press; 2018.
- [37] Kristjánsson Á, Moldoveanu A, Jóhannesson Ól, et al. Designing sensory-substitution devices: principles, pitfalls and potential. *Restor Neurol Neurosci*. 2016;34(5):769–787. doi:10.3233/rnn-160647.
- [38] Nicholson J, Kemp-Wheeler S, Griffiths D. Distress arising from the end of a guide dog partnership. *Anthrozoös*. 1995;8(2):100–110. doi:10.2752/089279395787156419.
- [39] Deci EL, Ryan RM. The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: human needs and the self determination of behavior. *Psychol Inquiry*. 2000;11(4):227–268. doi:10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01.
- [40] Reis HT, Sheldon KM, Gable SL, et al. Daily well-being: the role of autonomy, competence, and relatedness. *Pers Soc Psychol Bull*. 2000;26(4):419–435. doi:10.1177/0146167200266002.

Appendix A: The interview guide

General information

- How frequently do you travel?
 - Do you travel for vacation or for work?
 - Where do you usually stay overnight?
- When you go to hotels, do you go alone or with a companion?
 - If with a companion, who tends to accompany you? Is the companion indispensable?
- Are the hotels that you go to adapted for visually impaired people?
 - If so, which adaptations do you find useful (or not)?
 - If not, what adaptations would you consider desirable?

Challenges due to visual condition

- What are the main difficulties that you encounter during hotel stays?
 - Follow up if issues related to mobility or object localization are mentioned
- How do you find your room the first time you go there?
 - And subsequent times?
 - Do you have any routines when walking through the corridors?
- When you first enter your room, what is the first thing that you do?
 - And subsequent times?
 - Do you have any routines in this regard?
 - Follow up if issues related the spatial exploration of the room or moving within the room are mentioned
- Are there particular objects or obstacles that are annoying during locomotion in the corridor or in the room?

Aids for locomotion and object localization

- Have you ever used electronic aids for locomotion or object localization?
 - If so, which ones? Did you like them?
 - If not, are you aware of electronic aids that you have not tried yet?
 - If new aids exist, where do you think that you would hear about them?
- Do you think that innovations will help blind individuals substantially better in the future than is the case today?
 - If yes, how do you think that may happen?
 - If not, why not?

Final question: Do you have any further remark or suggestion about the foregoing?

Appendix B: List of themes and codes with relevant verbatims

Themes and subthemes	Codes ^a	Exemplary verbatims	
Navigation and orientation <i>Challenges</i>	Accessibility (hotel entrance and hallways, <i>elevator</i> , bedroom, bathroom)	"That day we found an elevator with a touch screen panel. And we were pressing but of course, you don't know which keys were pressed as it was all tactile" (P7).	
	Global localization (hotel entrance and hallways, <i>elevator</i> , bedroom, bathroom)	"If there are two elevators side by side, and you get into one or the other, they should still take you to the same general area. That shouldn't be too much of a problem. The real challenge, I think, is finding the elevator in the first place" (P2).	
	Local localization (<i>bedroom</i> , bathroom)	"Well, when you don't know the reception number, or when you are looking for the socket, you are walking with your hands on the wall and 'Man!' you don't find it" (P3).	
	Configuration (hotel entrance and hallways, <i>dining hall</i>)	"What worries me about going to a buffet ... the arrangement of tables, ... if you are blind, you are never going to find where dishes are displayed" (P6).	
	Signage	"But braille labels really solve my life. A lot, a lot. Because if they're well placed, they really solve the problem of getting around ... I mean, it's simple, but it's really very useful for us. It's very, very useful for people who know braille" (P8).	
	Obstacles (<i>hotel entrance and hallways</i> , terrace, bedroom, bathroom)	"You may go a little fast in a place where you don't expect anything, it is a clear space ... a hallway, but it can be uncomfortable if you hit tables, chairs, sofas" (P3).	
	Dependency on others	"The most difficult thing is getting from the lobby to your room, if there is no one to explain it to you" (P2).	
<i>Strategies</i>	Exploration	"So, I explore with my hands. Not with my hands in front of me, with my hands slightly parallel to my body, slightly forward, about 5 centimeters forward, like a half-moon. And when I find something that interests me, I feel it well" (P1).	
	Mental maps	"You have already made a route in your head" (P2).	
	Environmental cues (<i>tactile</i> , auditory)	"The floor is very useful for knowing here's a hallway, here's a change in texture, here's a room, an office, that can be very useful. But at the end of the day, when you are in a room, like a bedroom or something, you are not touching the floor all the time, you are touching the bed, the nightstand, the living room table, the chairs" (P2).	
	Spatial directions	"When I reach, someone often guides a little. I have good spatial location in my head and if someone tells me three doors to the right hallway or to the left, I usually understand it well and can usually store it and practice" (P3).	
Wayfinding aids <i>Non-technological</i>	Dog benefits (<i>autonomy</i> , navigation efficiency, sense of security)	"A guide dog can be very versatile, it provides autonomy but only if it has the ability to act independently and maintain its own autonomy" (P1).	
	Dog challenges (narrow space navigation, maintenance and health problems, <i>attachment issues</i>)	"I was lucky with my first dog. I mean, objectively speaking, outside of the affection I have for it, the dog turned out well. For now, I don't think I am going to get another one" (P7).	
	Cane benefit (navigating narrow and public spaces, exploration, <i>connection to environment</i>)	"I think the cane will always be very useful for marking the distance between the user and the object" (P2).	
	Cane challenges (<i>limited obstacle detection</i> , reduced mobility, careful navigation)	"Detecting a column can be skipped by a cane. As there was a big column ... he [the staff member] could see it, but I could not see it. And he made an arc around the column, and in that arc, while sweeping with the cane, there was an area that remained unexplored. Which usually works fine. But it is not guaranteed that the cane will always detect it" (P3).	
	Situational use of cane or dog	"I do all the routes with a dog, but if, at any given moment, the dog needs to stay behind, I have no limitation on my autonomy to use the cane" (P2).	
<i>Technological</i>	Utility of technology	"I really find NaviLens useful in labelling spices" (P1).	
	Lack of utility	"Look, I've tested Sunu device before ... personally, I didn't find it useful ... same with the UltraCane, which was another similar device. I haven't found Sunu [band] helpful beyond a few specific situations. I mean, I bought one, I have it, and now it just stays in a drawer. And I still go out, I move around, I go to [different] places every day ... so no, it hasn't really made any difference for me. Maybe someone else would find it useful, but for me, not so much" (P1).	
	Limited information	"The only flaw I see with the Seeing AI is that it does not read the display. So, of course, there are many appliances that show information on a seven-segment display, the old ones. And Seeing AI doesn't read it ... they could put that option, a seven-segment display reading option" (P2).	
	Overload of information	"In Madrid, with a lot of people, there were so many obstacles, and it was constantly beeping, and in the end, you get dizzy ... and discriminating is very difficult ... I haven't tried it there [in open spaces]. I have tried it in Madrid city, and it really didn't solve much for me" (P3).	
	Financial concerns	"But it [a cane with auditory information] is expensive in most situations ... I think this is the most important problem" (P5).	
	User needs <i>Autonomy</i>	Need for autonomy	"If I can solve something by myself, I don't want someone else to have to do it, because it is true that you often need help" (P6).
	Aid from others	"I usually go with someone as I would need help in commuting ... the train stations are huge spaces, and I always like to have someone there to help me" (P5).	

(continued)

Appendix B: Continued

Themes and subthemes	Codes ^a	Exemplary verbatims
	Need for understanding the environment	"As soon as I enter the room I want to know where everything is ... the table, where is the window, where is the door, where is the bathroom, what is inside the bathroom, where is the toilet [seat], where is the shower" (P5).
<i>Control over environment</i>	Need for exploring the surrounding	"Man, the logical thing is that if you go alone you need to do some exploring" (P6).
	Need for control	"It is convenient if you have your own apartment, or rented, but always the same [place], so that you go to a known environment where you probably have a controlled environment" (P6).
<i>Sociability</i>	Making the environment compatible	"And on my desk, I always have things in the same position. Then I can say, okay, these are my white or colored socks, or these are my black socks, always in the same spaces ... this allows a bit of control" (P5).
	Need for sociability	"If I go to Vienna right now, what will I be doing there? I contact El Corte Inglés [travel agency] to arrange the trip, I take myself to the airport, I explore it with a guide ... I don't see fun in it, that's why I like to travel with someone" (P3).
	Social concerns	"What is no longer the same is that you can ask someone on the street for help, which is another possible solution, but you don't always have someone who can help you. So, this is already a dependency " (P3).

^aIn several cases, a single verbatim is given for a group of codes. In such cases, the individual codes are indicated within parentheses, with the code corresponding to the exemplary verbatim being italicized.